

Optimized UKF-based perception of a repetitive dynamic event

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Abstract— Living beings are rarely passive observers. Instead, they are characterized by a "Perception-Action Coupling", i.e. they perceive in order to move and they move in order to perceive, which constitutes an essential loop for learning. Drawing inspiration from nature, this work proposes a novel method for minimizing the uncertainty of the information gathered when observing a Repetitive Dynamic Event (RDE), considering a sensor that can change its position and orientation. The method considers an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) for fusing the sensor's measurements with the evolution of the current dynamical model of the observed RDE. The proposed method aims at finding the optimum UKF parameters and pose of the sensor, for maximizing the quality of the estimation. Simulation and experimental evaluations show the improvement achieved by the proposed method, as compared to using a non-optimized UKF, in terms of the quality of acquired information of a dynamic event. The experiments are conducted using a UR10e robotic manipulator with an eye-in-hand ZED 2 RGB-D camera.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Repetitive Dynamic Event (RDE) is considered to be an event, characterized by specific dynamics, that re-occurs in a repetitive manner. RDEs can be either natural, e.g. frequent gas or liquid leakage, swinging objects, motion of leaves during a day etc, or artificial, e.g. the execution of experiments for modelling a system or the execution of demonstrations by a human towards Learning from Demonstration (LbD) of a task. To model the RDEs (or to learn, in case of LbD), one has to accurately observe and perceive the system's state. The uncertainty involved in the state perception/estimation, e.g. due to measurements error, plays a significant role on the quality of modelling.

In the context of active perception, the problem of finding the so-called "Next Best View" (NBV) was firstly introduced in the field of computer vision and robotics by C.Connolly [1]. NBV-based solutions consider an active observer, i.e. a sensor having the ability to change its position and/or orientation in space, and aim towards finding the optimum pose of the sensor for maximizing the information gathered about the perceived object/scene. Since their first appearance, NBV methods have been expanded and applied across many fields and applications, such as 3D object reconstruction,

robot autonomous navigation, visual and quality inspection. In the literature, most works tackle the problem of object/scene reconstruction, with the majority of them employing machine learning, such as 3D Convolution Neural Networks, Curriculum and Reinforcement Learning, Point Cloud Networks and Random Trees, for finding the next best view [2]–[5]. Other applications involve pose estimation [6], [7], object recognition/classification [8], [9], while in the field of robotics, NBV has been particularly studied also in applications such as localization [10], [11], robot grasping [12], [13], trajectory planning and robot navigation [14]–[16], or even calibration [17]–[19]. Although, the notion of NBV has been considered in all the aforementioned fields, to the best of the authors' knowledge, it has not been previously employed to tackle the problem of actively estimating the state of an RDE, as they mainly consider static objects or scenes.

Kalman filtering, initially introduced by Rudolf E. Kálmán [20], is a state estimation technique, which is based on a dynamic model, possessing a certain uncertainty. According to Kalman filtering the estimate is calculated by fusing the measurement, which is assumed to incorporate a noise with known statistical characteristics, and the prediction based on the model of the observed phenomenon. As the original Kalman filter considers a linear model, more recent variants are proposed for handling non-linearities, with the most popular being the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) [21]. The advantage of UKF over EKF is that it employs statistical methods for inferring the Jacobian matrix of the system and therefore no analytic expression if it is required.

In this work, considering an active sensor, we propose a method that seeks for the optimal parameters and Next Best View, in order to minimize the uncertainty involved in the perception and estimation of the state of an RDE during its next occurrence (if natural) or execution (if artificial). The proposed method, builds upon our previous method [22], in which the specific problem of LbD was tackled. The advancements of this work, as compared to our previous work, are the following:

- The Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) is utilized for estimating the observed state of the system, which ensures optimal data fusion, as opposed to [22] in a weighted mean was utilized.
- The optimization problem is solved before the repetition of the event, i.e. we seek for the global overall optimum sensor pose and UKF parameters through simulations, as compared to [22] in which the problem was solved in realtime yielding a near-optimal (sub-optimal) solution.

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II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVE

Let us consider a Repetitive Dynamic Event (RDE), such as the repetitive execution of a physical experiment. Further, consider the availability of a sensor, e.g. a camera, that is able to alter its pose (position and orientation) in order to efficiently gain information. Let $\{S\}$ be the frame of the sensor, and $\mathbf{p}_s \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_s \in SO(3)$ be the position and orientation (in a rotation matrix form) of $\{S\}$ respectively. Without loss of generality, we assume that the RDE is associated with a Point Of Interest (POI)¹. Let $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the coordinates of the POI in Cartesian space. Further, let $\mathbf{x}(t) \triangleq [\mathbf{p}^\top(t) \ \dot{\mathbf{p}}^\top(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6$ be the state of the system, considering that the evolution of the system can be characterized by a second order differential equation. The RDE is considered to be modelled by an autonomous time-invariant dynamical system of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{a}), \quad \mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{x}_0, \\ \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq [\mathbf{I}_3 \quad \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3}] \mathbf{x}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the measured output, which reflects the position of the POI, \mathbf{I}_n is the $n \times n$ identity matrix, $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the initial state of the system, $\mathbf{0}_{n \times n}$ the $n \times n$ zero matrix, $\mathbf{f}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^6 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^6$ a non-linear (in general) mapping and $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ the parameters of the dynamical system that encode the dynamics of the system, with $m \in \mathbb{N}$ being their quantity. Given that the measurement gathered from the sensor yields after a sampling procedure in time, we consider a discrete time. The time-discretized system, incorporating the uncertainty of both modelling and measurement, is then given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_k &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a}) + \mathbf{q}_{k-1}, \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}) + \mathbf{v}_k, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a}) \triangleq \mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a})dt$, $\mathbf{q}_k \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the process noise (modelling error) and $\mathbf{v}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the measurement noise, with $dt \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being the discretization time interval and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ being the discrete time index. Both \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{v} are considered to be random variables with known normal distributions, i.e. $\mathbf{q} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_6, \mathbf{Q})$ and $\mathbf{v} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_3, \mathbf{\Sigma})$, with $\mathbf{Q} \in S_{++}^6$ and $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in S_{++}^3$ being the variance-covariance matrices of the process and measurement noise respectively, and S_{++}^n denoting the set of $n \times n$ positive definite matrices. We assume that $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is a variable of the pose of the sensor as well as the position of the POI. i.e. $\mathbf{\Sigma}(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y})$, which is reasonable for a wide range of sensors and task cases. One related example is the case of identifying the position of a POI with an RGB-D camera, where the uncertainty is relatively higher for the depth provided by the sensor, due to erroneous depth estimation, which is propagated to the whole position estimate using the back-projection mapping.

Our aim is to optimally estimate the state of the system in order to use it for possibly updating the considered model of the RDE. In other words, our aim is to estimate \mathbf{x}_k , in each repetition of the RDE, based on the available $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \mathbf{a})$

that currently approximates/models the system, which is probabilistically characterized by \mathbf{Q} and the measurement \mathbf{y}_k , which is probabilistically characterized by $\mathbf{\Sigma}$. To this aim, we employ the notion of Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) [23], which does not involve the analytic computation of the Jacobian of the system, in the expense of introducing a number of parameters that needs to be tuned. Given the difficulty involved in the tuning of the parameters and the fact that $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is considered to be a function of the pose of the sensor, the contribution of the proposed solution is that it automatically seeks for the optimal parameters of the UKF, as well as the optimal pose of the sensor (which in turn affects $\mathbf{\Sigma}$), in order to minimize the total uncertainty of the estimate that will be provided by the UKF during the next repetition of the event. Notice that the pose of the sensor is considered to be static during a single repetition of the event.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Preliminaries on the Unscented Kalman Filtering

The Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) belongs to the "family" of Non-Linear Kalman Filters and it is used for estimating/predicting the state of nonlinear systems. For handling the non-linearity of a system, most non-linear Kalman filters linearize the system at each time instance, and then utilize the basic Kalman filtering idea, which constitutes of fusing the prediction provided by the known dynamical system with the measurement, according to the known covariance of each one of them respectively. For linearizing the system, UKF builds upon the fact that statistics-based numerical approximation of the derivatives, and specifically of the Jacobian of $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$, is easier to perform and more generic than the analytic one.

Let $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ and $\mathbf{P}_{k,k} \in S_{++}^6$ be the state estimate provided by UKF and its covariance matrix respectively, at the k -th time instance. The core idea of Kalman filtering generally, is that the total estimate, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}$, arises after two stages, the "Prediction" stage and the "Update" stage. The novelty in UKF is that the estimation depends on the state distribution which is represented using a minimal set of carefully chosen sample points, the so-called "sigma-points". At the prediction stage, sigma-points are propagated/transformed through a mathematical expression which is called Unscented Transform (UT). For the needs of this paper, the Eric A. Wan and Rudolph van der Merwe approach for $M = 2N + 1$ sigma points selection of the UT is used; where $N \in \mathbb{N}$ is the number of state variables, which in our case is $N = 6$. According to this approach, the i -th sigma-point, denoted as $\mathcal{X}_{k,k}^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, is selected based on the following equation, at each step k :

$$\mathcal{X}_{k,k}^{(i)} = \begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}, & \text{for } i = 1 \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} + \left(\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \right)_i, & \text{for } i \in [2, N + 1] \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} - \left(\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \right)_i, & \text{for } i \in [N + 2, M] \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ a constant, whose selection will be given later, and $\left(\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \right)_i$ denotes the i -th column of $\sqrt{(N + \lambda) \mathbf{P}_{k,k}} \in S_{++}^N$. The latter square root can be

¹The extension for incorporating multiple POIs is straight forward.

calculated using the Cholesky decomposition. Taking into consideration the autonomous time-invariant dynamic model, given in (2), the intermediate estimate of the prediction stage and its associated covariance matrix are calculated to be the following:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} = \hat{\mathcal{X}}_k \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^N \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k,k-1} = \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k \mathbf{W} \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k^\top + \mathbf{Q}_k \in S_{++}^N \quad (5)$$

where

$$\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k \triangleq \left[\mathbf{f} \left(\mathcal{X}_{k-1,k-1}^{(1)} \right) \dots \mathbf{f} \left(\mathcal{X}_{k-1,k-1}^{(M)} \right) \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}, \quad (6)$$

\mathbf{Q}_k the value of process covariance at k , $\tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k \triangleq \hat{\mathcal{X}}_k - \mathbf{1}_M \otimes \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ and $\mathbf{w} = \left[\frac{\lambda}{N+\lambda} \quad \frac{1}{2(N+\lambda)} \quad \dots \quad \frac{1}{2(N+\lambda)} \right]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^M$, $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag} \left(\frac{\lambda}{N+\lambda} + (1 - \alpha^2) + \beta, \frac{1}{2(N+\lambda)} \mathbf{I}_{2N} \right) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, with $\alpha \in (0, 1], \beta \in (0, \bar{\beta}]$ being tunable parameters, " \otimes " denoting the Kronecker product and $\mathbf{1}_M \in \mathbb{R}^M$ the all-ones vector, i.e. $\mathbf{1}_M^\top \otimes \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} = [\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} \dots \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1}]$ with $\bar{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being a preselected upper bound for β . Given a specific selection of α, λ is defined as $\lambda = (\alpha^2 - 1)N$.

Let $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the measurement at the k -th step. In the update stage, the measurement is taken into account for the final calculation of the state estimate, denoted with $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and the total estimation covariance matrix, denoted with $\mathbf{P}_{k,k} \in S_{++}^N$, at each time step, as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1} + \mathbf{K}_k (\mathbf{y}_k - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_k), \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k,k} = \mathbf{P}_{k,k-1} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{P}_{y,k} \mathbf{K}_k^\top, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k \triangleq \mathbf{Y}_k \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_k \triangleq \mathbf{P}_{xy,k} \mathbf{P}_{y,k}^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_k \triangleq \left[\mathbf{g} \left((\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k)_1 \right) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{g} \left((\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k)_M \right) \right], \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{y,k} \triangleq \mathbf{A} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{A}^\top + \Sigma(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y}_k) \in S_{++}^N, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{xy,k} \triangleq \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{A}^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}, \quad (13)$$

with $\mathbf{A} \triangleq \mathbf{Y}_k - \mathbf{1}_M^\top \otimes \hat{\mathbf{y}}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$.

B. Optimization problem formulation and solution

Notice that as the sensor is considered to be able to change its pose, both \mathbf{p}_s and \mathbf{R}_s are considered to be parameters that can be pre-selected to improve the estimation. Let $\mathbf{p}_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the Center of the Scene (CoS), which is assumed to be predefined and $d_s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ be the nominal sensing distance of the sensor, e.g. for the RGB-D cameras d_s should be selected within the range in which the distance estimation is available. Based on \mathbf{p}_c and d_s , we parameterize the pose of the sensor, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s$, using the angles $\theta \in [0, 2\pi], \phi \in [0, \pi]$ of the polar coordinates of the position of the sensor. For considering a hemisphere instead of a sphere, e.g. in cases in which the event is evolved above a supporting surface, one could consider the range of ϕ to be $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$. More specifically, we define an allowable sphere around \mathbf{p}_c for the position of the sensor, as shown in Fig.1, while for the orientation,

Fig. 1: The concept of finding the optimal pose of the sensor. The dotted ellipses represent the covariance of the uncertainty of the sensor.

the parameterization corresponds to the poses in which the sensor's z -axis (which is considered to be the axis along the sensor's direction) is always pointing towards \mathbf{p}_c . Given the above, an example of the exact parameterization of the pose is provided by the following expressions:

$$\mathbf{p}_s(\theta, \phi) = \mathbf{p}_c + d_s [c(\phi) \quad s(\phi)c(\theta) \quad s(\phi)s(\theta)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_s(\theta, \phi) = [\mathbf{x}_s \quad \tilde{\mathbf{p}} \times \mathbf{x}_s \quad \tilde{\mathbf{p}}] \in SO(3), \quad (15)$$

where $c(\cdot) \equiv \cos(\cdot), s(\cdot) \equiv \sin(\cdot), \tilde{\mathbf{p}} \triangleq \frac{\mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{p}_s(\theta, \phi)}{\|\mathbf{p}_c - \mathbf{p}_s(\theta, \phi)\|} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ and $\mathbf{x}_s(\theta, \phi) \triangleq \frac{[0 \ 0 \ 1]^\top \times \tilde{\mathbf{p}}(\theta, \phi)}{\|[0 \ 0 \ 1]^\top \times \tilde{\mathbf{p}}(\theta, \phi)\|}$, with " \times " denoting the cross product and " \mathbb{S}^2 " the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^3 . Based on the above the covariance matrix reflecting the uncertainty of the measurement, i.e. Σ , becomes a function of θ, ϕ .

Remark 1. Notice that it is straight forward to involve any other smooth 2-dof allowable manifold, instead of (14), (15), based on the task requirements or sensor specifications.

Let $\xi \triangleq [\alpha \ \beta \ \theta \ \phi]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$ be the vector of parameters that can be tuned for adjusting the quality of the state estimation through UKF. Further, let $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$ be the ellipsoid of the covariance matrix $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$, where $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{B}) \triangleq \{\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^N : \mathbf{z}^\top \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{z} = 1\}$, for any $\mathbf{B} \in S_{++}^N$. The volume of $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$ is proportional to $\det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$. Our goal is to find the optimal set of parameters, denoted with ξ^* , that minimizes the uncertainty of the state estimation trough UKF, reflected by $\det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$. As $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$ is variable in time (i.e. at each k), we are aiming towards solving the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi^* = \arg \min_{\xi} \sum_{k=1}^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt, \\ \text{s. t. } \alpha \in (0, 1], \beta \in (0, \bar{\beta}], \\ \theta \in [0, 2\pi], \phi \in [0, \pi], \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\bar{k} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the duration of the event in discrete time.

As our aim is to find the optimum set of parameters, i.e. ξ^* , before the start of the observation of the repetition of the RDE, we propose the offline solution of (16). To this aim, in order to get the value of $\sum_{k=1}^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt$ for a specific ξ ,

we simulate the observation iteration for the given parameter set by adding an artificial process noise, i.e. \mathbf{q}_k , based on the covariance matrix \mathbf{Q}_k , to the simulated evolution of the current model. Furthermore, as the actual ground-truth evolution is not known, the last corrective term of (7) is omitted, which however does not heavily affect the nature of $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$, on which we focus in this part. For solving the optimization problem, the Covariance matrix adaptation evolution strategy (CMA-ES) is selected, in which the exploration is dictated by a covariance matrix, updated based on the confidence of the solution. The complete function for calculating the cost utilized as the core for CMA-ES, i.e. $\sum_{k=1}^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt$, is provided in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Calculation of cost function for a specific ξ

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1: Input:  $\xi$ 
2: Known:  $\Sigma(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y}_k), \mathbf{Q}_k, dt, \mathbf{x}_0, \bar{k}$ 
3: Initialize  $\mathbf{x}_0$  and  $\mathbf{P}_{0,0} = \mathbf{Q}_0$ 
4: for  $k \in [1, \bar{k}]$  do ▷ Simulation loop
5:   Compute  $\mathcal{X}_{k,k}^{(i)}, \forall i = 1, \dots, 2N + 1$  from (3)
6:   Generate artificial  $\mathbf{q} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_N, \mathbf{Q}_k)$ 
7:   Compute  $\hat{\mathcal{X}}_k$  from (6) and (2)
8:   Compute  $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k-1}$  and  $\mathbf{P}_{k,k-1}$  from (4) and (5)
9:   Calculate (9)-(13)
10:  Approximate  $\mathbf{y}_k$ , by setting  $\mathbf{y}_k = \hat{\mathbf{y}}_k$ 
11:  Compute  $\Sigma(\mathbf{p}_s, \mathbf{R}_s, \mathbf{y}_k)$  for  $\xi$ 
12:  Compute  $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}$  from (7)
13:  Compute  $\mathbf{P}_{k,k}$  from (8)
14:  Store  $\det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k})$ 
15: end for
16: Output:  $\sum_1^{\bar{k}} \det(\mathbf{P}_{k,k}) dt$ 

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IV. SIMULATION STUDY

For evaluating the robustness of the proposed method given different initial conditions, we conduct numerical simulations in Python and Matlab (the code is provided in the GitHub repository of the experiments), considering the case of estimating the state of a spherical object, having a mass of $m = 1\text{kg}$, rolling within a spherical constraint (radius equal to $L = 1\text{m}$), considering a viscous friction of $b = 0.04\text{Ns/m}$. Towards this direction, for the ground-truth dynamical system we consider: $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_1)\mathbf{x}_2 \\ \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_1) \left(\mathbf{g}_r - \frac{b}{m}\mathbf{x}_2 \right) \end{bmatrix}$, where $\mathbf{x}_1 \triangleq \mathbf{p}$, $\mathbf{g}_r \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ -g]^\top$ is the gravity vector and $\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}_1) \triangleq \mathbf{I}_3 - \frac{(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{p}_c)(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{p}_c)^\top}{\|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{p}_c\|^2}$ is the tangential to the sphere projection matrix, while \mathbf{p}_c is selected to be at the center of the sphere of motion. For the simulations, a hemisphere having a radius of $d_c = 5\text{m}$ is considered as the set of allowable positions of the camera, while the process noise is assumed to be characterized by $\mathbf{Q}_k = \text{diag}(2, 0.1, 0.1, 10, 1, 1) \times 10^{-2}, \forall k = 1, \dots, \bar{k}$, reflecting the case in which the modelling mainly involves an error along the x -axis. The sensor sampling period is considered to be $dt = 0.033\text{s}$, corresponding to a camera sensor set to capture 30 fps. The sensor's uncertainty is set

to $\Sigma = \mathbf{R}_s \text{diag}(0.01, 0.01, 0.2) \mathbf{R}_s^\top$, mimicking an RGB-D camera having a relatively larger uncertainty along the z -axis of $\{S\}$. The values of Σ are not tuned, but predefined reflecting standard deviation of the error equal to 10cm and 44cm, along the $x - y$ axes and z -axis (depth) of the camera respectively. Furthermore, we define a field of view, based on real RGB-D intrinsic parameters, and we set the uncertainty to a maximum value when the POI is not visible, i.e. if \mathbf{p} is not within the field of view, then $\Sigma = 5000\mathbf{I}_3$.

Figure 2 shows the resulted optimized poses (red stars) starting from 49 different initial poses (yellow points) of the sensors, after 80 iterations of the CMA-ES optimization algorithm, considering (16). The initial values of α and β are set to 0.1 and 1 respectively, while the upper bound of β is set to $\bar{\beta} = 5$. Notice, in Fig. 2, the general trend of the optimal poses to align the maximum uncertainty of the camera (i.e. z -axis of the camera) to the minimum uncertainty of the process noise (which is along the $y - z$ plane of the inertial frame). However, the optimal pose is also shaped by other UKF aspects (such as the distribution of the sigma points), and this is why the resulted poses are also seen to be gather in two regions (symmetrically close to the y -axis, which is the main direction of the velocity of POI). In Fig. 3 the estimate provided by the UKF is depicted for the 49th (last) case with the initial parameters being $\xi_0 = [0.1 \ 1 \ 1.047 \ 5.026]^\top$ and the optimal ones being found at $\xi^* = [0.98 \ 0.001 \ 0.95 \ 3.056]^\top$. In Fig. 3, both the results of the arbitrary initial selected non-optimal parameters ξ_0 and the optimal, ξ^* , are presented for comparison, alongside with the corresponding sensor measurements and the ground-truth position. Both the process and the measurement noises are generated using the corresponding normal distribution, i.e. \mathbf{Q} and Σ respectively. Notice the improvement of the estimation achieved (approximately 2.2 times smaller mean estimation error) after moving the camera to the optimal pose and using the parameters found by the proposed method.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

For validating the proposed method, experiments are conducted using a ZED 2 RGB-D camera, attached to the tip of a UR10e robot, as shown in Fig.4. A video recording of the experiments can be found in the following link: <https://youtube.com/shorts/JwgLR7wDzdg>. The task involves the estimation of the state (position and velocity) of a swinging pole, i.e. a pendulum. For detecting the tip of the pole a predetermined April-tag (<https://github.com/AprilRobotics/apriltag>) is utilized, as the detection of specific characteristics/features is outside of the focus of the paper. As the center of the scene (i.e. the center of the sphere of allowable poses), an arbitrary point is selected, close to the pendulum's evolution, namely $\mathbf{p}_c = [0.9 \ 0.28 \ 0.538]^\top \text{m}$, while the allowable sphere is selected to have a radius of $d_c = 0.5\text{m}$, being within the range in which ZED 2 can yield a depth estimate. The pivot point, as well as the exact length of the pole are considered to be parameters of the already modelled dynamical system that are however characterized by an uncertainty. Given the above, the process uncertainty,

Fig. 2: Optimization results for 49 different initial poses of the sensor (yellow dot). The z -axis are always pointing towards the center of the hemisphere.

is considered to be the following:

$$\mathbf{Q}_k = \text{diag}(\mathbf{U} \text{diag}(0.02^2, 0.02^2, 0.1^2) \mathbf{U}^\top, 0.01^2 \mathbf{I}_3), \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in SO(3)$ defines an orthonormal basis having its third column (z -axis) aligned to the estimated direction of the pole (based on the tip and the pivot point). The measurement uncertainty is considered to be similar to that of the simulations, as depth estimation (z -axis of the camera) is characterized by relatively higher uncertainty, adding also a term which is proportional to the April-tags visible area, namely: $\Sigma = (1 + \phi) \mathbf{R}_s \text{diag}(0.002, 0.002, 0.02)^2 \mathbf{R}_s^\top$ (in the considered allowable sphere expression, the higher the ϕ , the smaller the visible area of AprilTag from the camera). Note that when a "NaN", ∞ or $-\infty$ depth estimate is provided by the camera, the algorithm considers the minimum value, which is 0.45m.

The ranges of parameters α, β are set to be similar to the simulations, while the ranges of ϕ and θ are selected to be $[0, \pi/3]$ and $[\pi/2, 7\pi/6]$ respectively, based on the workspace of the robot. To move the robot from one pose to another, a first order Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics (CLIK) algorithm is utilized, sending velocity commands every 2ms to the robot. The whole method is implemented using an external PC that communicates with the robot through a point-to-point ethernet connection, while the code, written in Python, is accessible through GitHub².

The initial parameters for the optimization algorithm, is considered to be $\xi_0 = [0.5 \ 0.2 \ \pi/3 \ \pi/2]^\top$. Figure 5 shows the path estimated through UKF, comparing the cases of both the initial (without optimization) and the optimal pose and parameters found by the proposed method. These are found

Fig. 3: Comparison of estimation $\mathbf{H}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k,k}$ with and without optimized parameters. The norm of the estimation error is depicted in the last sub-plot. Dashed lines: The measured position of the POI, solid colored lines: the estimate for not optimized UKF parameters (blue), and for the optimized ones (red).

Fig. 4: Experiment using UR10e and ZED 2 as an eye-in-hand.

to be $\xi^* = [0.994 \ 0.386 \ 0.094 \ 1.148]^\top$ (both poses are provided in Fig. 4). Figure 6 depicts the estimated radius of curvature, $\hat{r} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, in each case, which ideally should remain constant. The standard deviation of \hat{r} is computed $\text{std}(\hat{r}) = 1.2\text{mm}$ with the proposed optimized estimation and $\text{std}(\hat{r}) = 7.3\text{mm}$ with the non-optimized one, i.e. more than six times higher. Through Fig. 5 and 6 one can notice the significant improvement, in terms of the quality, noise and smoothness in the estimates, achieved when observing the scene from the optimal pose and using the parameters provided by the proposed method. Further, notice the spikes occurred when the position of the POI is perceived from the

²<https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/ECC.OPTIMIZED.NBV.git>

arbitrary selected pose of the sensor, due to the small visible area of the AprilTag.

Fig. 5: Estimated position of the AprilTag, with and without using the optimal found parameters and pose. Black solid line: UKF estimate, Red dashed line: raw measurement from the camera.

Fig. 6: Estimated radius of curvature.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In the context of estimating the state of a Repetitive Dynamic Event through observation, and considering the availability of an active sensor, this work proposes a method for finding the Next Best View and optimal parameters of the state estimation through UKF. The method assumes that the sensor can alter its pose (i.e. it is actuated) through a mechanism and that the measurement uncertainty is a function of the pose (position and orientation) of the sensor in Cartesian space. The proposed method is evaluated through simulations and experiments using a ZED 2 RGB-D camera attached to the tip of a UR10e robot. The results show the improvement achieved, in terms of state estimation, when using the found optimal pose and parameters, as well as the robustness of the optimal seeking mechanism that uses the proposed cost function.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Connolly, "The determination of next best views," in *Proceedings. 1985 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 2, 1985, pp. 432–435.
- [2] Z. Yan, H. Yang, and H. Zha, "Active neural mapping," in *Intl. Conf. on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2023.
- [3] X. Chen, Q. Li, T. Wang, T. Xue, and J. Pang, "Gennbv: Generalizable next-best-view policy for active 3d reconstruction," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.16174*, 2024.

- [4] H. Dhimi, V. D. Sharma, and P. Tokekar, "Pred-nbv: Prediction-guided next-best-view planning for 3d object reconstruction," in *2023 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2023, pp. 7149–7154.
- [5] A. Bircher, M. Kamel, K. Alexis, H. Oleynikova, and R. Siegwart, "Receding horizon "next-best-view" planner for 3d exploration," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2016, pp. 1462–1468.
- [6] J. Sock, S. H. Kasaei, L. S. Lopes, and T.-K. Kim, "Multi-view 6d object pose estimation and camera motion planning using rgbd images," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW)*, 2017, pp. 2228–2235.
- [7] A. Doumanoglou, R. Kouskouridas, S. Malassiotis, and T.-K. Kim, "Recovering 6d object pose and predicting next-best-view in the crowd," in *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2016, pp. 3583–3592.
- [8] Z. Wu, S. Song, A. Khosla, F. Yu, L. Zhang, X. Tang, and J. Xiao, "3d shapenets: A deep representation for volumetric shapes," in *2015 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2015, pp. 1912–1920.
- [9] C. Korbach, M. D. Solbach, R. Memmesheimer, D. Paulus, and J. K. Tsotsos, "Next-best-view estimation based on deep reinforcement learning for active object classification," *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2110.06766, 2021.
- [10] G. Costante, J. A. Delmerico, M. Werlberger, P. Valigi, and D. Scaramuzza, "Exploiting photometric information for planning under uncertainty," in *International Symposium of Robotics Research*, 2015.
- [11] Z. Zhang and D. Scaramuzza, "Beyond point clouds: Fisher information field for active visual localization," *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 5986–5992, 2019.
- [12] Y. Wu, Y. Zhang, D. Zhu, X. Chen, S. Coleman, W. Sun, X. Hu, and Z. Deng, "Object slam-based active mapping and robotic grasping," *2021 International Conference on 3D Vision (3DV)*, pp. 1372–1381, 2020.
- [13] D. Morrison, P. Corke, and J. Leitner, "Multi-view picking: Next-best-view reaching for improved grasping in clutter," *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 8762–8768, 2018.
- [14] M. Lodel, B. Brito, A. Serra-Gómez, L. Ferranti, R. Babuška, and J. Alonso-Mora, "Where to look next: Learning viewpoint recommendations for informative trajectory planning," in *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE Press, 2022, p. 4466–4472. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA46639.2022.9812190>
- [15] S. Tankasala, R. Mart'in-Mart'in, and M. Pryor, "Beyond shortsighted navigation: Merging best view trajectory planning with robot navigation," *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2408.12513, 2024.
- [16] Z. Ma and J. Chen, "Adaptive path planning method for uavs in complex environments," *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, vol. 115, p. 103133, 2022.
- [17] J. Yang, J. Rebello, and S. L. Waslander, "Next-best-view selection for robot eye-in-hand calibration," *2023 20th Conference on Robots and Vision (CRV)*, pp. 161–168, 2023.
- [18] J. Rebello, A. Das, and S. Waslander, "Autonomous active calibration of a dynamic camera cluster using next-best-view," in *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2017, pp. 1484–1489.
- [19] X. Zhang, Y. Xi, Z. Huang, L. Zheng, H. Huang, Y. Xiong, and K. Xu, "Active hand-eye calibration via online accuracy-driven next-best-view selection," *Vis. Comput.*, vol. 39, no. 1, p. 381–391, Jan. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00371-021-02336-7>
- [20] R. E. Kalman, "A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems," *Journal of Basic Engineering*, vol. 82, no. 1, pp. 35–45, 03 1960. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3662552>
- [21] S. Julier and J. Uhlmann, "Unscented filtering and nonlinear estimation," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 92, no. 3, pp. 401–422, 2004.
- [22] D. Papageorgiou, N. Kounalakis, N. Efsthopoulos, J. Fasoulas, and M. Sfakiotakis, "Active: An active perception framework for skill transfer through iterative visual observations," in *2024 32nd Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED)*, 2024, pp. 94–100.
- [23] E. Wan and R. Van Der Merwe, "The unscented kalman filter for nonlinear estimation," in *Proceedings of the IEEE 2000 Adaptive Systems for Signal Processing, Communications, and Control Symposium (Cat. No.00EX373)*, 2000, pp. 153–158.